

FROM INTERNS TO AMBASSADORS: ASSESSING HOW POLICE TRAINING PROGRAMS INFLUENCE PUBLIC PERCEPTION AND ORGANIZATIONAL IMAGE

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the effect of PPVIP on participants' perceptions regarding the internship program, public trust, and the soft image of the Punjab Police. For this study, a sample of 117 participants completed the questionnaires measuring these constructs. The results indicated that age did not moderate perceptions, suggesting that perceived program effectiveness did not differ across age groups. Gender differences existed in ratings for the internship program, as females viewed the internship more positively than males, although gender did not have a significant effect on either public trust or the police's soft image. Participants who rated the program as Excellent demonstrated higher perceptions of program effectiveness, greater public trust, and a more favorable soft image. Engaging in internships outside PPVIP did not significantly alter perceptions. Structural equation modeling subsequently confirmed these findings. All measurement indicators for PPVIP, Public Trust (PT), and Soft Image of the Punjab Police (SIPP) were loaded significantly onto their latent constructs, which reflects strong validity and reliability. The SEM showed that PPVIP has a strongly positive effect on public trust ($\beta = 0.728$) and that public trust has a very strong positive effect on the soft image of the police ($\beta = 0.879$). The direct effect of PPVIP on soft image was negligible ($\beta = -0.042$), which could suggest that public trust acts as a mediator to translate these program experiences into organizational image perceptions. Well-structured, quality police intern programs can enhance participant engagement, build public trust, and create an improved organizational image for law enforcement. Agencies can use such programs to encourage gender-inclusive approaches, improve community-police relations, and develop program participants as ambassadors to influence public perceptions positively.

Keywords: Police internship programs, public trust, organizational image, community policing, experiential learning, organizational socialization..

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between law enforcement agencies and the communities they serve is a critical determinant of effective policing (Brage et al., 2019; Imam, 2022; Mastrofski). Public trust

and the perceived legitimacy of police organizations shape citizens' willingness to cooperate, comply with laws, and participate in crime prevention initiatives ((Mazerolle et al.,

2013; Tyler & Fagan, 2008; Tyler & Huo, 2002). Over the past decade, structured police internship and volunteer programs have emerged as innovative strategies aimed at improving public engagement and organizational transparency (Askerbaevich, 2024; Modise, 2023). These programs nurture not only participants' professional competencies but also ambassadors who can positively influence community perceptions about the police (Haarr, 2001; Padilla et al., 2023). The Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program in Pakistan is one such initiative, purposed to enhance participants' competencies while strengthening public trust and enhancing the soft image of the Punjab Police (Sager et al., 2025; Manzoor et al., 2025). Police internship programs concurrently achieve various purposes: professional skill development, community involvement, and image building for the organization. Research suggests that well-structured internship programs not only give practical experience to the participants but also raise awareness about the organizational values and enhance interpersonal skills, which are very helpful in constructive citizen engagement (Druhum et al., 2024; Fielding, 2023; Haarr, 2001). On the other hand, the indirect impact of these internship programs is an assurance that well-trained volunteers will deal with citizens in a nondiscriminatory, open, and professional manner that will help in gaining the confidence of the community and proving the positive intentions of the organization. In areas like Punjab, Pakistan, where police-community relations have been damaged due to historical, socio-political, and institutional reasons, programs such as PPVIP assume greater significance for ensuring constructive engagement and changing the public's perception of law enforcement. While many police agencies in recent times have embraced this internship approach to policing, little empirical evidence exists that explains its impact, and most of the relevant research has focused on either general police training or community policing strategies. Most of the literature does not specifically analyze participants' perceptions or investigate the impact of demographic influences like age and gender on those perceptions. Understanding the

mechanisms through which such programs achieve their intended goals is tied to questions of design inclusivity that are sensitive to participant heterogeneity. For instance, adopting gender-sensitive approaches might ensure equal participation and take into account possible differences in program reception. Similarly, age-related differences should be studied in order to ensure the best engagement strategies across the participant spectrum.

1.1 Research Objectives

1. To study how the participants view the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program and its impact on public trust and improving the police's soft image.
2. The demographic factors of age and gender on participants' perceptions and outcomes.
3. To examine how participant ratings of the program are related to perceptions of program effectiveness, public trust, and organizational image.

1.2 Research Questions

1. How do participants perceive the PPVIP, and how does this affect public trust and the soft image of the police?
2. Do age and gender influence participants' perceptions and PPVIP-related outcomes?
3. How are participants' ratings of the PPVIP related to perceptions of program effectiveness, public trust, and the police's soft image?

1.3 Hypotheses

1. H1: There are no significant differences among participants of different age groups in their perceptions about PPVIP, public trust, and the soft image of Punjab Police.
2. H2: Female participants will report more positive perceptions of the internship program compared to male participants.
3. H3: Higher program ratings will be linked to stronger perceptions of program effectiveness, greater public trust, and a more positive soft image.

2. Literature Review

The need for the strong bonding between police organizations and the communities they serve is

being viewed internationally as a cornerstone of law enforcement effectiveness. Public trust, as well as legitimacy, affects citizens' compliance with laws, readiness to cooperate, and participation in crime prevention programs accordingly. Tyler (2006) Thus, law enforcement agencies have increasingly used community-oriented initiatives such as internship and volunteer programs in order to develop positive contact and improve organizational image. Skogan (2006) Recent studies undertaken in Pakistan also resonate on the significance of trust and community engagement in influencing police legitimacy. For example, Hassan (2025) demonstrated that factors of procedural justice-including timely investigations, respect, and transparency-are significant predictors of trust in the police. Similarly, capacity-building pursuits and structured community policing initiatives across Punjab have been shown to enhance organizational effectiveness and trust-building (Manzoor et al., 2025).

2.1 Police Internship Programs and Professional Development

Internship and volunteer programs in policing serve multiple functions. First, they offer participants hands-on experience, professional skills, and organizational and interpersonal competencies for community engagement (Kappeler et al., 2020). Organized programs like the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program are designed to train participants but also create ambassadors with the capabilities to work between the police and the people. As Tyler (2010) stated, this kind of program can enhance organizational values and ethics and give volunteers experience that can translate into active responsibilities between citizens and police. Empirical examinations have generally concluded that participants in police internship programs often report increased confidence in their ability to contribute to community safety, improved understanding of law enforcement protocols, and heightened awareness of social responsibilities. In Pakistan, a comparative study of community and conventional policing in Sindh illustrated the fact that the adoption of citizen-centric programs, emphasizing volunteer involvement and building

trust, significantly enhanced public perception and police legitimacy. These individual-level outcomes can add up to increase the perceived legitimacy of the police, leading toward a softer, more approachable organizational image and community cooperation. This is reflected in Skogan's observation that programs assuring equity, transparency, and professionalism may positively affect public perception indirectly through volunteers.

2.2 Public Trust and Organizational Image

Public trust is a significant construct in assessing the effectiveness of law enforcement interventions. According to Tyler, trust in authorities is developed based on perceptions of procedural fairness, transparency, and accountability (Tyler, 2006). The police internship has the potential to impact trust directly-exposing participants to ethical organizational practices-and indirectly, as participants diffuse their positive experiences throughout their social networks (Tyler, 2017). A "soft image" of the police refers to the concept of law enforcement viewed in a friendly, cooperative, socially responsible manner, as opposed to a more rigid or authoritarian image. Programs like PPVIP are crucial in fostering this soft image in terms of the well-trained volunteers interacting professionally with the community (Cordner, 2014). Recent studies in Pakistan also confirm the previous view. Hassan (2025) noted that procedural justice acts to engage public confidence, while Manzoor et al. (2025) illustrated how capacity-building initiatives, framed by formal training and evaluation, improve community response and the perceived legitimacy of police. Put together, these findings indicate that more appropriately designed programs of interns and volunteers have the capacity to help develop the competencies of participants while strengthening the public's view of police legitimacy. For instance, other studies suggest that age and gender impact perception of police programs. For example, based on participant age, interpretation of training content may vary or there may be a varying emphasis on the skill acquired or community impact derived from police contact (Reisig & Parks, 2004). Gender may also contribute to such bias; female participants may evaluate the

component parts of the program quite differently, possibly because of differences in communication style, socialization experiences, or expectations concerning professional development (Rabe-Hemp et al., 2023). These demographic effects are important to consider in any research effort aimed at crafting inclusive programs, which take into account maximum involvement and effectiveness.

2.3 Theoretical Underpinnings

The current study is based on two major theoretical underpinnings: Social Learning Theory by Bandura and Walters (1977) and Organizational Socialization Theory by Van Maanen and Schein (1977). According to Social Learning Theory, knowledge, behavior, and attitudes are acquired through observation, imitation, and modeling of others within a social context. In the context of police internships, professional norms, ethical standards, and interpersonal skills are learned through observation of experienced officers, engagement in real-world tasks, and receipt of structured feedback. Such experiential learning reinforces both skill acquisition and attitudinal shifts that could promote positive perceptions of the organization. Organizational Socialization Theory complements such a perspective by describing how individuals adapt to new roles and socialize into the culture of organizations through planned experiences. Socialization through internship programs offers opportunities to learn organizational hierarchies, values, and behaviors while developing a sense of fit within an organization. The process of effective socialization can increase participants' confidence, professional identity, and alignment with organizational goals. Such aspects potentially lead to positive perceptions about program effectiveness, public trust, and, in turn, may transfer into organizational image (Van Maanen & Schein, 1977). In support of these theories, Manzoor et al. (2025) illustrated that improved training, evaluation, and capacity-building initiatives within Punjab strongly corresponded to increased community policing outputs and levels of public trust. The study integrates these theoretical standpoints, conceptualizing PPVIP as a learning and socialization mechanism whereby the

experiences of participants affect individual competencies and perceptions of the Punjab Police as a community-oriented and trustworthy institution. While structured police internship programs are gaining recognition, empirical studies that evaluate the effects on participants' perceptions, public trust, and organizational image remain scant, particularly in the South Asian context. Previous research has largely focused on either traditional training or community policing initiatives without examining how participants' demographic characteristics, program ratings, or prior internship experiences may moderate outcomes (Tyler, 2017; Cordner, 2014). The present study fills this void by empirically testing the PPVIP, measuring participant perceptions across multiple constructs, while considering demographic influences and subjective program evaluations. This study also contributes to practice by presenting actionable insights for law enforcement agencies in Pakistan. These findings can feed into program design by emphasizing the importance of high-quality training components, gender-sensitive strategies, and mechanisms for ongoing evaluation. By fostering positive participant experiences, structured internship programs are better positioned to enhance individual competencies, public trust, and the organizational image of police institutions.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey design to examine the impact of the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program (PPVIP) on participants' perceptions of the program, public trust in the Punjab Police, and the organization's soft image. The research further investigated whether demographic factors, including age and gender, participants' program ratings, and prior internship experiences influenced these perceptions. A quantitative approach was selected to enable statistical testing of group differences and relationships between variables, providing robust empirical evidence on program effectiveness (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). The study sample consisted of 117 individuals who had completed the PPVIP, encompassing a diverse range of university students and young

professionals from Punjab, Pakistan, with ages ranging from 18 to 35 years and a gender distribution of 58% male and 42% female respondents. To explore potential influences of prior experiences, participants were categorized based on whether they had participated in additional internship programs outside PPVIP (Bryman, 2016). The survey instrument comprised three primary constructs. First, perceptions of the PPVIP were measured using a 10-item scale assessing participants' satisfaction, perceived skill development, and engagement with the program (Kappeler et al., 2020). Second, Public Trust was evaluated using an 8-item scale examining participants' trust in the Punjab Police, including perceptions of transparency, fairness, and accountability (Tyler, 2006). Third, the Soft Image of the Punjab Police was measured using a 9-item scale assessing participants' perceptions of the police as approachable, professional, and community-oriented (Skogan, 2006). All items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("Strongly Disagree") to 5 ("Strongly Agree"), providing a standardized approach for assessing participants' attitudes and perceptions across the three constructs.

3.2 Reliability and Validity of the Scales

Internal consistency for each scale was determined by Cronbach's alpha; high reliability was found across both PPVIP ($\alpha = 0.89$), Public Trust ($\alpha = 0.87$), and Soft Image ($\alpha = 0.85$), indicating consistent measurement suitable for statistical analysis (Field, 2024). Convergent and discriminant validities were checked via PLS-SEM 4 by means of the factor loadings, composite reliability, and average variance extracted. All indicators showed significant loadings with their respective latent constructs ($\lambda > 0.50$), thus confirming convergent validity, while the square roots of AVE were above the interconstruct correlations, thus confirming discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2014). The relationships among the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program, Public Trust, and the Soft Image of the Punjab Police were analyzed through the application of Structural Equation Modeling with PLS-SEM Version 4. The hypothesized model tested the direct effect of PPVIP on Public Trust, the direct

effect of Public Trust on Soft Image, and the indirect effect of PPVIP on Soft Image through Public Trust. PLS-SEM was chosen because the method is suitable for small to medium sample sizes, can handle data that are non-normal, and allows predictive modeling of complex theories (Hair et al., 2014). Therefore, the strength and significance of the proposed relationships were estimated, showing standardized path coefficients, t-values, and significance levels based on bootstrapping with 3,000 resamples. The quality of the model was checked by R^2 , Q^2 , and SRMR values, ensuring that the model was both explanatory and predictive.

3.3 Procedure

Participants completed the survey online through secure links shared via university mailing lists and program coordinators. All participants provided informed consent, and anonymity was guaranteed. The survey asked several demographic questions: age, gender, and prior internship experience; it then proceeded with the three scales, assessing PPVIP perceptions, public trust, and soft image. Also, participants rated the program overall as Excellent, Good, Neutral, Poor, or Very Poor, which served as an independent variable in subsequent analyses (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

3.4 Data Analysis

Data analysis was done with SPSS Version 25 for descriptive and inferential statistics and PLS-SEM 4 for the structural modeling. Descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, were determined for all variables. All statistical tests were conducted at a 95% confidence level ($p < .05$). Effect sizes for testing the magnitude of differences and relationships were estimated with Cohen's d for t-tests and eta-squared for ANOVA.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The study followed ethical guidelines for conducting research on human participants. Data collection was done anonymously to assure privacy. Participation was voluntary, and the respondents were also informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty (American Psychological Association, 2020).

4. Results

The research design for this study has enabled the thorough investigation of the influence of PPVIP on participants' perceptions, public trust, and soft image concerning the Punjab Police. The reliable scales, structured demographic analysis, and robust statistical procedures like ANOVA and t-tests were useful in the identification of important

trends and inferences, especially related to the impact of program ratings and gender differences. These findings thus constitute empirical evidence for guiding law enforcement agencies to design appropriate, non-discriminatory, and community-oriented internship programs to help build confidence among citizens (Kappeler et al., 2020; Tyler, 2006; Skogan, 2006).

Table 1. Effect of age on the participants' perceptions PPVIP, PT, and SIPP

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	117	45.30	4.583	.424	44.46	46.14	30	50
Public Trust	116	43.58	6.472	.601	42.39	44.77	8	50
Soft Image of Punjab Police	114	44.41	5.303	.497	43.43	45.40	30	50

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	46.973	2	23.487	1.120	.330
Public Trust	213.107	2	106.553	2.616	.078
Soft Image of Punjab Police	145.539	2	72.770	2.664	.074

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of age on the participants' perceptions of three constructs: the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program (PPVIP), Public Trust (PT), and Soft Image of Punjab Police (SIPP). Results showed that there were no statistically significant variance across age groups - 18-20 years, 21-25 years, and 26-35 years - in terms of perceptions of

the internship program, $F(2, 114) = 1.12, p = .330$. Similarly, age did not significantly influence participants' perceptions of public trust, $F(2, 113) = 2.62, p = .078$. Also, it did not have any significant influence on the soft image of Punjab Police, $F(2, 111) = 2.66, p = .074$. While the mean score for the age group from 26 to 35 years was slightly higher regarding PPVIP, $M = 48.00$; PT, M

= 48.67; SIPP, $M = 49.00$, compared with the rest of the age groups, these differences are not significant. This leads to the conclusion that

perceptions of the quality of the internship program, its impact on public trust, and its contribution to improving the police's soft image are uniform across the different age groups.

Table 2. Effect of gender on the participants' perceptions PPVIP, PT, and SIPP

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	Male	24	43.88	5.093	1.040	41.72	46.03	30	50
	Female	91	45.84	4.124	.432	44.98	46.69	34	50
	Prefer not to say	2	38.00	11.314	8.000	-63.65	139.65	30	46
	Total	117	45.30	4.583	.424	44.46	46.14	30	50
Public Trust	Male	24	43.63	5.632	1.150	41.25	46.00	32	50
	Female	90	43.67	6.536	.689	42.30	45.04	8	50
	Prefer not to say	2	39.00	15.556	11.000	-100.77	178.77	28	50
	Total	116	43.58	6.472	.601	42.39	44.77	8	50
Soft Image of Punjab Police	Male	24	43.38	5.984	1.222	40.85	45.90	30	50
	Female	88	44.80	4.885	.521	43.76	45.83	31	50
	Prefer not to say	2	40.00	14.142	10.000	-87.06	167.06	30	50
	Total	114	44.41	5.303	.497	43.43	45.40	30	50

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	181.377	2	90.689	4.584	.012
	2255.152	114	19.782		
	2436.530	116			
Public Trust	42.677	2	21.338	.505	.605
	4773.625	113	42.244		
	4816.302	115			
Soft Image of Punjab Police	77.680	2	38.840	1.391	.253
	3099.943	111	27.927		
	3177.623	113			

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of gender on participants' perceptions of three constructs: Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program (PPVIP), Public Trust (PT), and Soft Image of Punjab Police (SIPP). Results showed that there was a statistically significant difference among gender groups for the internship program, $F(2, 114) = 4.58, p = .012$, thus providing support that gender significantly influenced the participants' assessment of the internship

program. Female participants ($M = 45.84, SD = 4.12$) had higher perceptions of the internship program as compared to the male participants ($M = 43.88, SD = 5.09$). However, nonsignificant differences in gender were found to influence perceptions of Public Trust, $F(2, 113) = 0.51, p = .605$, or the soft image of Punjab Police, $F(2, 111) = 1.39, p = .253$. This indicates that even though female participants considered the internship program more favorable, gender did not

significantly influence perceptions associated with public trust or the police's soft image.

Table 3. Effect of rating on the participants' perceptions PPVIP, PT, and SIPP

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	Excellent	93	46.63	3.482	.361	45.92	47.35	37	50
	Good	19	40.89	3.814	.875	39.06	42.73	34	48
	Neutral	3	36.67	5.774	3.333	22.32	51.01	30	40
	Poor	1	30.00	30	30
	Very Poor	1	46.00	46	46
	Total	117	45.30	4.583	.424	44.46	46.14	30	50
Public Trust	Excellent	92	44.53	6.396	.667	43.21	45.86	8	50
	Good	19	39.84	4.913	1.127	37.47	42.21	31	50
	Neutral	3	36.00	6.928	4.000	18.79	53.21	28	40
	Poor	1	43.00	43	43
	Very Poor	1	50.00	50	50
	Total	116	43.58	6.472	.601	42.39	44.77	8	50
Soft Image of Punjab Police	Excellent	91	45.30	4.795	.503	44.30	46.30	31	50
	Good	18	40.61	5.248	1.237	38.00	43.22	30	50
	Neutral	3	36.67	5.774	3.333	22.32	51.01	30	40
	Poor	1	50.00	50	50
	Very Poor	1	50.00	50	50
	Total	114	44.41	5.303	.497	43.43	45.40	30	50

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	992.504	4	248.126	19.245	.000
	1444.026	112	12.893		
	2436.530	116			
Public Trust	562.873	4	140.718	3.672	.008
	4253.428	111	38.319		
	4816.302	115			
Soft Image of Punjab Police	573.689	4	143.422	6.004	.000
	2603.933	109	23.889		
	3177.623	113			

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to explore the effect of ratings assigned by participants to the Punjab Police Volunteers Internship Program, which were categorized as Excellent, Good, Neutral, Poor, and Very Poor, on perceptions pertaining to the internship program, public trust, and the soft image of the Punjab Police. Results showed that there was a statistically significant effect of program rating on the perceptions about

the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program, $F(4, 112) = 19.25, p < .001$, thus indicating that the participants' evaluations of the internship significantly differed among the rating levels. To be sure, those who rated the program as Excellent ($M = 46.63, SD = 3.48$) reported more favorable perceptions compared to those who rated it as Good ($M = 40.89, SD = 3.81$) or Neutral ($M = 36.67, SD = 5.77$). There was also a significant

difference in Public Trust scores by rating level, $F(4, 111) = 3.67, p = .008$. Participants who rated the program as Excellent ($M = 44.53, SD = 6.40$) had higher levels of public trust than those rating it as Good ($M = 39.84, SD = 4.91$) or Neutral ($M = 36.00, SD = 6.93$). The main effect for the Soft Image of Punjab Police also turned out to be significant, $F(4, 109) = 6.00, p < .001$. The respondents who rated the internship program as

Excellent ($M = 45.30, SD = 4.80$) perceived a better soft image of the Punjab Police than those who rated it as Good ($M = 40.61, SD = 5.25$) or Neutral ($M = 36.67, SD = 5.77$). Overall, these findings suggest that the higher the satisfaction with the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program, the stronger the perceptions of program effectiveness, greater public trust, and more favorable soft image of the Punjab Police.

Table 4. Effect of additional training on the participants' perceptions PPVIP, PT, and SIPP

Group Statistics		Received internships	additional	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	Yes			48	45.33	4.507	.651
	No			69	45.28	4.668	.562
Public Trust	Yes			48	44.31	5.292	.764
	No			68	43.06	7.182	.871
Soft Image of Punjab Police	Yes			47	45.21	4.881	.712
	No			67	43.85	5.547	.678

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program	.139	.710	.067	115	.947	.058	.865	-1.656	1.772
Public Trust	1.389	.241	1.028	114	.306	1.254	1.220	-1.163	3.670
Soft Image of Punjab Police	.907	.343	1.355	112	.178	1.362	1.005	-.630	3.354

Therefore, an independent samples t-test was conducted to determine if participants with additional internship experience beyond PPVIP viewed the internship program differently, in terms of public trust (PT) and Soft Image of Punjab Police (SIPP), compared to participants without any additional experience. The results showed no significant difference between participants with additional internship experience and participants with no additional internship

experience in rating the internship program, $t(115) = 0.07, p = .947$, with mean scores of 45.33 ($SD = 4.51$) and 45.28 ($SD = 4.67$) for participants with and without additional internship experience, respectively. Similarly, there were no significant differences on Public Trust, $t(114) = 1.03, p = .306$, or the Soft Image of Punjab Police, $t(112) = 1.36, p = .178$. Thus, the results suggest that having prior internship experience other than PPVIP did not significantly influence participants'

views regarding the quality of the program, its impact on public trust, or how well it helped the police improve their soft image.

Figure 1. Contributing factor for soft image of Punjab Police

Figure 1 depicts a structural equation model that probes the relationships between the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program (PPVIP), Public Trust (PT), and the Soft Image of the Punjab Police (SIPP). The model presents factor loadings for individual observed indicators and standardized path coefficients for the latent constructs. All ten observed indicators, PPVIP1-PPVIP10, load significantly onto the latent construct PPVIP with standardized loadings ranging from 0.523 to 0.787. The highest loading was that for PPVIP6, "The trainers effectively engaged participants and encouraged interaction" ($\lambda = 0.787$), implying that this item makes the strongest contribution to measuring the internship program construct. The lowest loading was for PPVIP1, "The internship program provided high-quality learning materials and resources" ($\lambda = 0.523$), which is within acceptable ranges as per Hair et al. (2014). These factor loadings reflect the strength of the relationship between each observed indicator and the underlying latent construct, confirming that the PPVIP construct is reliably measured by its indicators. Similarly, all ten observed indicators (PT1-PT10) load strongly onto the latent

construct Public Trust, with standardized loadings ranging from 0.732 to 0.851. The highest loading is PT5 ("I ensure that my interactions with the public will be fair and unbiased") ($\lambda = 0.851$), and the lowest is PT3 ("My internship will equip me with the skills needed to handle public concerns effectively") ($\lambda = 0.780$). These loadings show that each item meaningfully contributes to the construct. All the values are above the generally accepted threshold of 0.50, indicating the existence of convergent validity (Hair et al., 2014). In the measurement of the SIPP construct, all nine indicators, SIPP1 to SIPP9, have high standardized loadings ranging between 0.672 and 0.868. The highest loading was from SIPP9, which is "The internship program will help me contribute positively to police-community dialogues and trust-building activities" ($\lambda = 0.868$), while the lowest was SIPP6, "The media will highlight more positive stories about Punjab Police due to our community engagement efforts" ($\lambda = 0.672$). This gives evidence that Soft Image as a latent construct is well reflected by its observed indicators and maintains internal consistency. It is reflected by a path coefficient from PPVIP to Public Trust of 0.728, thus showing a strong positive relationship. Such a coefficient suggests

that the participants' perceptions about the internship program significantly relate to the high level of public trust in the Punjab Police. The path coefficient from Public Trust to SIPP is 0.879, reflecting a very strong positive relationship. This means that increased public trust significantly contributes to an enhanced perceived soft image of police; this concurs with theoretical expectations that institutional trust leads to a favorable organizational reputation (Tyler, 2006). The path between PPVIP (program engagement) and SIPP is negative and negligible in magnitude ($\beta = -0.042$), indicating that the impact of the internship program on the police's soft image is largely indirect and is mediated through public trust. The model supports the notion that the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program is positive for public trust, which strongly influences the soft image of the Punjab Police. The negligible direct influence of PPVIP on SIPP shows how public trust acts as a buffer between participants' experiences with the program and their perceptions of organizational image. In sum, all measurement indicators feature strong loadings, thus underpinning both the construct validity and reliability of all latent variables. The factor loadings reported signify that every observable item meaningfully and significantly represents its respective latent construct, hence giving confidence in the robustness of the SEM.

5. Discussion

This study investigated the impacts of the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program on the perception of its participants, public trust, and the soft image of the Punjab Police. The findings provide empirical and theoretical insights into how structured police internship programs can shape both individual and organizational outcomes.

5.1 Participants' Perceptions of PPVIP

The overall survey results show that participants generally reported positive perceptions of the internship program, which reflected satisfaction with the program quality, engagement, and skill development. Gender differences emerged, with female participants rating the program more

positively than males, consistent with prior research suggesting women may evaluate collaborative and participatory training experiences more favorably (Rabe-Hemp et al., 2023; Yousaf et al., 2024). Age did not significantly relate to perceptions, indicating that the design of the program effectively engages participants across a broad age range, consistent with prior studies highlighting the universal applicability of structured professional development programs (Tyler, 2017; Noreen & Iqbal, 2025). Furthermore, participants' overall ratings of the program are strongly linked with outcomes in that those rating the program as Excellent reported higher perceptions of program effectiveness, higher levels of trust, and a more positive soft image. This points to participant satisfaction and program quality as key determinants of program impact, a finding consistent with experiential learning theory, which suggests that engaging experiences and meaningful participation amplify learning and attitudinal outcomes (Bandura & Walters, 1977; Van Maanen & Schein, 1977).

5.2 Public Trust and Soft Image of the Police

The survey results and PLS-SEM analysis together underlined the pivotal role of public trust in mediating the influence of PPVIP on organizational image. The SEM model revealed a strong positive effect of PPVIP perceptions on Public Trust ($\beta = 0.728$) and a very strong positive effect of Public Trust on the Soft Image of the Police ($\beta = 0.879$). The negligible direct effect of PPVIP on soft image ($\beta = -0.042$) suggests that the participants' positive experiences with the program enhance the perceived image of the Punjab Police primarily through building trust. This is in line with Tyler's (2006) procedural justice framework, which posits trust as a mechanism for legitimizing institutions. These findings suggest that the structured, high-quality internships develop not only individual skills but also result in organizational reputation gains when participants consider the program fair, transparent, and engaging. It is in this respect that building trust has emerged as an important intermediary outcome in police-community

engagement programs, a notion that received recent support from evidence out of Pakistan that citizen-oriented police programs have positive effects on perceptions of legitimacy and public accountability.

5.3 Role of Demographic and Experiential Factors

It was also observed that there was no significant difference in perceptions for those who had previously had an internship experience outside of PPVIP, further underlining the unique value of the PPVIP experience. This confirms that structured and organizationally tailored training programs provide better outcomes than generic experiences (Cordner, 2014). Gender differences in program evaluation confirm that programs need to be designed with consideration of gender sensitivity, such that female participants' perspectives inform strategies for improving engagement. Age insensitivity of the outcomes suggests that well-structured internships can effectively engage a diverse participant pool, strengthening inclusivity and broadening program reach.

5.4 Theoretical Implications

The findings support both Social Learning Theory (Bandura & Walters, 1977) and Organizational Socialization Theory (Van Maanen & Schein, 1977), showing how observational learning, experiential engagement, and professional socialization within the internship program form participants' attitudes and perceptions of the police organization. SEM results specify how the experiential learning influences organizational image indirectly through nurturing trust, which in turn mediates participants' perceptions of the police as approachable, professional, and community-oriented. This mediating pathway adds empirical validation for the mechanism through which structured internships build organizational legitimacy. From a practical perspective, the findings of this study suggest that law enforcement agencies may strategically use structured internship programs to create ambassadors, build public trust, and improve the soft image of the organization. The quality of the program, through engaging trainers, relevant

content, and participatory activities, is paramount in maximizing the satisfaction of participants. Further, a gender-sensitive design will therefore consider differential responses to training components for enhanced inclusivity and overall engagement. Continuous evaluation regarding participant feedback and program outcomes will be paramount in refining program elements for enhanced effectiveness. Further, the enhancement of trust by fair, transparent, and ethical interaction will also enhance, indirectly, the police's public image. Overall, the study has established that the Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program shapes participants' perceptions, which are translated into increased public trust, thereby predicting a more favorable soft image of the Punjab Police. Integration of the survey results with PLS-SEM provides robust empirical evidence that structured internships function not only as educational interventions but also as strategic instruments for improving organizational reputation and fostering constructive community engagement.

6. Conclusion

This study develops empirical evidence regarding the impact of PPVIP on participants' perceptions and public trust in the organizational soft image of the Punjab Police. The results show that perceptions regarding the program are generally positive; female participants rated it higher than males, while age did not have any differential impact on outcomes. Participants' ratings of the program were strongly associated with perceptions of program effectiveness, public trust, and organizational image, emphasizing participant satisfaction and the importance of program quality. Results from the PLS-SEM reveal that the effect of PPVIP on the soft image of the police is mainly indirect, through public trust. The program contributes significantly to enhancing public trust ($\beta = 0.728$), which itself is a strong predictor of a favorable soft image of the police ($\beta = 0.879$). The negligible direct effect of the program on the soft image itself, $\beta = -0.042$, underlines the idea that building trust is the primary mechanism by which structured internships affect organizational reputation. These

findings support both Social Learning Theory and Organizational Socialization Theory, as experiential learning and structured socialization within a police internship program are found to build participants' skills while simultaneously cultivating positive perceptions about the police as accessible, professional, and community-oriented. This study contributes to the scant empirical research in South Asia on police internship programs by underscoring the importance of context-specific, well-structured training initiatives in facilitating positive organizational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, some recommendations that may guide the design and implementation of police internship programs include the following. First, maximizing participant satisfaction a factor that will have a positive influence on public trust and the organizational image entails improving program quality through the inclusion of engaging trainers, interactive sessions, and relevant content. Second, equitable participation and satisfaction can be promoted by the adoption of gender-inclusive strategies in the design of program components to accommodate female participants' learning style and engagement preference. Third, a greater emphasis on activities that can build trust within exercises, as well as initiatives at community engagement, demonstrates fairness, transparency, and ethical practices to increase public trust—a key mediator for positive organizational perceptions. Fourth, ongoing evaluation through regular assessment of participant feedback and program outcomes allows the refinement of programs, ensuring their improved effectiveness in achieving organizational objectives. Fifth, highlighting experiential learning through active participation, observation, and mentorship opportunities reinforces the development of skills in participants, coupled with an improvement in attitudes toward the organization. Lastly, using alumni as ambassadors enables program graduates to serve as promoters of the police's soft image in the community, thus reinforcing the indirect influence of structured internships on public perception. The Punjab Police Volunteers' Internship Program is thus an effective model of

how structured police internships could be utilized in leveraging better participant competencies, public trust, and the organizational image of law enforcement agencies. Police organizations may integrate high-quality program design, gender-sensitive approaches, a mechanism for building trust, and alumni involvement to create informed ambassadors that enhance community-police relations.

Authors' Contributions

The contributions by authors are as follows: The conceptualization of the study, literature review, methodology design, and collection of data were performed by Laiba Abbas Butt. Data analysis, interpretation of results, PLS-SEM modeling, and revision of the manuscript were carried out by Abbas Rashid Butt. [Third Author's Name] contributed to the survey design, participant coordination, and validation of measures and reviewed the manuscript. All authors contributed to the critical revisions, read and approved the final version of the manuscript, and agreed on being accountable for all aspects of this work.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors do not declare any conflict of interest regarding this work.

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